

concentrations but are not truly mutants (see table).

Preliminary studies on the chromosome number of the regenerated

plants show aneuploidy, a chromosomal abnormality that may have been induced by the prolonged exposure of the calli to the *in vitro* culture

conditions.

This is the first report on green plant regeneration from salt-stressed, long-term somatic cell culture. *ℳ*

Effect of sucrose on callus induction and plant regeneration in Taipei 309

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The influence of sucrose on the callusing ability of japonica rice variety Taipei 309 anthers was compared in three induction media: N6, potato medium, and E 10 (modified B5). The N6 and potato media had 60 and 120 g sucrose with 2 mg 2,4-D/liter. The E10 medium had 20, 60, and 120 g sucrose in addition to 5 g glucose/liter with 1 mg 2,4-D/liter, 0.5 mg BAP/ liter, and 0.5 mg IAA/ liter. Regeneration for all treatments was done in standard MS medium with 30 g sucrose/ liter, 1 mg kinetin/ liter, and 1 mg NAA/ liter.

All calli transferred for regeneration were healthy and compactly growing, with a pale yellowish white appearance. But only 9-22% differentiated into green plants in the treatments. Some calli produced green as well as albino

Influence of sucrose on callusing of anthers and differentiation of plantlets in Taipei 309.^a IRRRI, 1986.

Medium	Sucrose concentration (%)	Inoculated anthers (no.)	Callusing anthers (%)	Calli (no.) transferred for regeneration	Calli (no.) differentiating into		
					Green or + albino plantlets	Albino plantlets only	Roots only
N6	6	800	23	198	34	23	7
N6 A	12	850	32	209	45	36	10
P	6	900	26	216	20	35	12
PA	12	800	37	245	40	47	14
E10	2	900	20	197	22	11	9
E10 A	6	900	28	234	37	33	15
E10 B	12	950	45	283	51	48	22

^a N6, E10, and potato media were used for callus induction, and MS medium for plantlet regeneration.

plantlets. Altering the cytokinin-auxin ratio of the regeneration medium to 2 mg kinetin/liter + 0.5 mg NAA/ liter did not change the differentiation pattern.

In calli induced by the N6 medium, more calli differentiated into green plants than into albinos. The reverse pattern appeared with the potato medium. On the E10 medium (B5), green and albino plantlets were

produced in about equal proportions (see table). About 36% of the calli that differentiated produced roots only. In all three media, at higher sucrose levels more calli and more green plants were produced, although the frequency of albino plants was also higher.

Results indicate that higher concentrations of sucrose can be advantageously used to increase green plantlet regeneration. *ℳ*

Heat treatment to increase callus induction efficiency in anther culture of IR42

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Indica rices are generally regarded as recalcitrant varieties in anther culture because of their low, if ever, callus production and plant regeneration efficiencies. IR42 is one of the more important IR varieties because of its resistance to major insect pests and diseases and high yielding ability. One of the drawbacks to its popularity in farmers' fields, however, is its late maturity. It is important to get variants that not only retain IR42's agronomic characteristics but also are early maturing. Anther culture can be a potential tool for producing such

variants but the problem of callus induction and plant regeneration efficiencies should first be solved. By applying heat treatment to rice panicles before culturing the anthers and manipulating media components, we were able to increase callus production in IR42.

Rice panicles with 5-10 cm distance between the auricle of the flag leaf and that of the subtending leaf were collected for the study. Each panicle was divided into the upper and bottom portions and a floret was collected from the middle section of each half for determination of the stage of pollen development. Only anthers with pollen grains between the mid-uninucleate to early binucleate stages of development were plated. The remaining spikelets of each portion were divided into 3 lots and placed separately in petri dishes

Effect of heat treatment on callus induction efficiency in IR42 anther culture.

Treatment	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (no.)	% callus production
<i>E10 medium</i>			
H ₀	345	34	9.8
H ₅	623	76	12.2
H ₁₅	439	90	20.5
<i>ER medium</i>			
H ₀	565	64	11.3
H ₅	706	102	14.4
H ₁₅	577	84	14.6

containing 1.5% water agar. Each lot was subjected to 1 of the following heat treatments at 35 °C: 0, 5, and 15 min, followed by a cold treatment at 10 °C for 7 d. Anthers from all treatments were plated in two media which contain the salts and vitamins of Gamborg's B5 medium but differ in growth regulators. E10 contained 0.5 g benzyladenine/liter,